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Proposal: Hate speech detection For Afaan Oromo
Social Media posts and Comments

Group members

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Acronyms

BLR	Bayesian Logistic Regression
RFDT	Random Forest Decision Tree
SVM	Support Vector Machines
LSTM	Long Short Term Memory
FDRE	Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia
TF-IDF	

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

According to [1], the Oromo peoples are the biggest ethnic group in the Horn of Africa. They live in a land that extends from north eastern Ethiopia to east central Kenya and in eastern Sudan and in eastern Somalia [2]. The Oromo speak a common language called “Afaan Oromo”. This language is categorized as eastern Cushitic family [3]. [2], states that as there is no agreement among scholars about the population of the Oromo, but a consensus seems to reveal that within the present-day Ethiopia alone the Oromo account either the majority or a half of the total population.

The Oromo, according to [4], referring [5], noted that the Oromo are divided into five Yayyabaa (major groups). These are: the Tuulamaa and the Macca, the Sabboo and the Goonaa, the Rayyaa and the Aseboo, the Siikkoo and the Mando and the Ituu and the Humbaanaa. Oromo speakers can be found all over Ethiopia, and abroad than the resident population in Ethiopia. In United States, Australia, Canada and different Europe cities people are speaking.

The Oromo people communicates through social media using Oromo language, known as Afaan Oromo. Since Social media as a means of communication can disseminate information quickly and widely, making it not only as a means of friendship and various information, but also used as a means of trading, dissemination of government policies, political campaigns and religious preaching [6]. In recent years, the exponential growth of social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn has been increasingly exploited for the propagation of hate speech. Social media has both positive and negative impact in social, economic and political activities of one country. The positive impacts are it helps peoples to exchange opinion digitally and globally and also help peoples to promote product through social media without payment. But the negative impact of social media is dissemination of hate speeches which is attacking peoples based on characteristics like race, ethnicity, gender, and sexual orientation, or threats of violence towards others. Though there is no formal definition exists but there is a consensus that it is speech that targets disadvantaged social groups in a manner that is potentially harmful to them.

Drawing upon these definitions, we define hate speech language that is used to expresses hatred towards a targeted group or is intended to be derogatory the members of the group. In extreme

cases this may also be language that threatens or incites violence, but it does not include all instances of offensive language because people often use terms that are highly offensive to certain groups but in a qualitatively different way. Hate speech is an unfortunately common occurrence on the Internet and in some cases culminates in severe threats to individuals group of people by verbal attacks and promotion of hatred based on the basis of race, ethnicity and national origin.to overcome the problem on social media many researchers are try to detect hatred by using machine learning and natural language processing over different languages. But this paper proposes machine learning approach to detect hate speeches.

1.2. Defining Hate Speech

According to [7], One reason hate speech is difficult to define is that it exists at the intersection of several related types of expression: Discriminatory language which disparages people based on a shared identify; Generalization which, regardless of intent, stereotypes people based on a shared identify; Dangerous speech which incites or presages violence (hate crime); Symbolic (non-verbal) expression, e.g. swastikas, repurposed emojis and memes. These different aspects also pose a significant challenge for automation.

Defines hate speech as: Any expression, regardless of offensiveness, which broadly characterizes a specific group of people based on malignant, qualitative, and/or subjective attributes, particularly if those attributes pertain to: ethnicity, nationality, religion, nationality, religion, sexuality, disability, class.

In accordance with Article 55(1) of the Constitution of the FDRE, it is hereby proclaimed as follows; **Speech** means the act of disseminating of information verbally, textually, graphically or by other means. **Hate speech** means speech that deliberately promotes hatred, discrimination or attack against a person or a discernable group of identity, based on ethnicity, religion, race, gender or disability [8].

There are three key paradigms which are able to provide differing yet illuminative lenses to better understand the issue and the implications of hate speech acts [9].

Concept: The practice of labelling hate speech as such can be particularly harmful in itself and serves to outperform other fundamental rights, so caution must be applied when identifying hate speech acts as such. At what point does offensive speech become hate speech? Ultimately, there must be a boundary between the tolerable and the intolerable, in other words, under what

circumstances does condemnation, insult or scorn be rightfully categorized as a message of harassment, inhumanity and degradation; and therefore unacceptable?

Context: It is important to question the role which context plays in determining whether damaging and provocative speech amounts to hate speech. In the case of deeply divided societies, longstanding historical and social currents have often led to entrenched inequality and communal violence. Hate speech law is fundamentally shaped by ideological, historical, and social context and therefore it is specific to each country, whilst also sitting alongside international conventions and legislations.

Teaching humans to detect written hate speech is difficult. Teaching machines is exponentially more difficult [7]. Like as Loan words, patois, mixed languages, Misspellings, Homonyms, Obfuscation, Location of conversation are what many of challenges in context.

Example In wollega the word which is Bukkee is “beside” But in Arsi Bukkee is “Sexless”.

Transmission: Which media should be taken into consideration when mapping hate speech? This is a particularly pertinent issue as access to the Internet increases, and social media platforms are being favoured over traditional outlets, such as radio and print media, for the expression of hate speech. Hate speech can also disseminated in other unconventional arenas including SMS messages and song lyrics, and it is also important to consider the non-textual media through which hate speech may be carried, for instance through symbols and gestures, art and image.

1.3. Motivation

Our first and great sense that made us to study this research work is that, were different studies has been performed on Hate Speech detections and classifications for most of the time by different languages. In the current world, the development of every country is dependent on the technology implemented as per their culture, religion, economic level, and social background like their language. In our country Ethiopia, have no tool to detect hate speech. However, the evolution of the Internet and of social media texts, such as Twitter, Facebook and YouTube messages, has created many new opportunities for creating such tools. Afaan Oromo is one of the Ethiopian Languages which is written in its own unique script and it can be written with Latin script.

Hate message are prevalent and challenging in the Ethiopian online community as individuals spread hate message through social media. Possibly leads into acts of violence or hate crimes and destroys the lives of individuals, families, communities and the country at large. Therefore, its

great important to monitor and identify instances of hate speech, as soon as possible to prevent their spread on social network.

Because of ease of data collection, the vast majority of studies have been conducted using English language Twitter data, and therefore do not necessarily tell us very much about other platforms or cultural contexts[10]. It is very important to conduct the hate speech detection in another languages like Afaan Oromo and another platform as well.

2. Literature review

Several works have done on hate speech detection in English [11], [12] and [13]. In these studies, the researchers used machine learning approach on twitter data set collected from twitter. In [12], the study was focus on detecting hate speech against black people by using Naive Bayes algorithm and word unigram as the feature. Three annotators that consist of people who have a different racial background are assigned for labelling the data set.

Article [13] focus on more general that covers ethnic group, race, ethnicity, religion, etc. Bag of words technique was also implemented, using unigram and bigram features. In this study, BLR, RFDT, and SVM have the same performance to detect hate speech on tweets in English, achieving performance of 77% on the F-measure score.

As far as we know no more work is done before on this area in Afan Oromo and the first work done in Ethiopian languages is [14] that is in Amharic language. In this paper the authors have built a corpus of Amharic comments from public pages of Ethiopian newspapers, politicians, activists, TV and Radio broadcast and groups by using Facepager. They used Word2Vec and TF-IDF for feature selection and Naïve Bayes and Random forest machine learning algorithms for classification. The model was trained on data set of 4,882 comments and tested on data set of 1,238 comments to classify whether the post and comments are hate or not and able to detect and classify in an accuracy of 79.83 % and 65.34% for Naïve Bayes with word2vec feature vector and Random Forest with TF-IDF feature modeling approach respectively.

Another study in this area is done on Indonesian language [15] by creating a new dataset that covers hate speech in general, including hatred for religion, race, ethnicity, and gender. In this report, the researcher has carried out the preliminary study on the machine learning approaches for

text classification. The study compared the performance of several features and machine learning algorithms for hate speech detection. Features that extracted were word n-gram with n=1 and n=2, character n-gram with n=3 and n=4, and negative sentiment. Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Bayesian Logistic Regression, and Random Forest Decision Tree are used for classification. An F-measure of 93.5% was achieved when using word n-gram feature with Random Forest Decision Tree algorithm. According to the evaluation results word n-gram feature outperformed character n-gram.

In reference [16], the three categories of hate in Italian language from Facebook platform are identified: the first category is Strong hate, Weak hate and No hate, the second category is No hate and Hate, and the last category is obtained by merging the Strong hate and Weak hate classes. For classification they used two classification algorithms: the first based on Support Vector Machines (SVM) and the second on a particular Recurrent Neural Network named Long Short Term Memory (LSTM). The researcher's finding shows that, on Strong hate, Weak hate and No hate classes SVM achieved an accuracy of 64.61% whereas the LSTM achieved 60.50% on Hate and No hate classes LSTM performed well 75.23% accuracy and SVM achieved 72.95% of accuracy.

3. Statement Problem

The challenge of wrangling hate speech is an ancient one, but the scale, personalization, and velocity of today's hate speech a uniquely modern dilemma. While there is no exact definition of hate speech, in general, it is speech that is intended not just to insult or mock, but to harass and cause lasting pain by attacking something uniquely dear to the target. Hate speech has been especially prevalent in online forums, chat rooms, and social media.

Recent events have shown that the social media is being used as a playground for the hate speech, defamation, fake news while the government unable to control those problems and also very difficult to identify hate speech traditionally.

Now day social media affect the daily life of the society because of hate speech posted by individual or group who in the name of political activism disseminate hate full speech online and members of the local population indirectly or directly participate in the violent activities across the different region of the country.

Even, possibly leads into acts hate crimes or jail. In [8], according to proclamation; Any person who commits acts proscribed under Article 4 shall be punished with simple imprisonment not

exceeding two years or up to 100,000 birrs. If an attack against a person or a group has been committed as a result of a hate speech, the punishment shall be from 1-5 years. Any person who commits acts proscribed under Article 5 shall be punished one year or up to 50,000 birrs. If the offense of hate speech or disinformation offense has been committed through a social media account having more than 5,000 followers or through a broadcast service or print media, the person responsible for the act shall be punished three years or up to 100,000 birrs.

Hate speech may face the problem of political, social, religion conflict between individual and group of peoples those may cause loss of resource, life and support terrorism and violence. Even if it does not intensify prejudice and stereotypes but also affects the mental health of the targeted individuals. This research proposed the development of a model that classify speech as hate speech or not. This classification will significantly improve the process of detecting hate speech on social media by reducing the amount of time and human effort required.

Even though Afaan Oromo is one of the major languages widely spoken and written in Ethiopia, there is no research conducted on the area of social media hate speech detection. Hence, due to the absence of social media hate speech detection for Afaan Oromo, people are not enjoying the social media even most of them are not using the social media. In this study we are going to build a model that can classify Afaan Oromo Facebook posts and comments as hate and no hate.

4. Objective

4.1. General objective

The general objective of this research is to design a model hate speech detection for Afaan Oromo Facebook comments and posts by using machine learning method.

4.2. Specific objective

To achieve the aforementioned general objectives the following specific tasks have been performed:

- ✓ Review relevant works in other languages with different approach.
- ✓ Develop hate speech corpus that are collected from Afaan Oromo Facebook pages and used for training and test purpose.
- ✓ Develop Afaan Oromo hate speech detection model.
- ✓ Develop a prototype of the proposed system.

- ✓ Evaluate the performance of the proposed system.

5. Scope and Limitation

Hate speech detection is very complex and a huge task that demands a lot of resources and effort. Since there is no formal way to identify offensive language, hate speech or neither of them. The main goal of this study is detecting Afaan Oromo hate speech on data Facebook comment and posts.

6. Significance of the study.

The study has many advantageous in terms of hate speech concepts. Detecting and removing hate speech is important for online communities for maintaining safe environments for its users and as a responsibility considering their impact on society.

Hate speech detection system will help for reduction of time and human effort to identify verbal attack on social media. The system will help to filter any hatred comment and post that makes peoples of the local population indirectly or directly participate in the violent activities across the different region of the country. The result of this research also used as input for further research investigation in the area of hate speech detection. And it plays a great role in daily life.

7. Research Methodology

The purpose of this section is to present the methods and procedures that going to use in carrying out the study. Attempt will be made to describe step by step, the methods, procedures and other devices that will be used to collect, analyze and interpret data. It also shows what steps will be taken to ascertain the validity and reliability of instruments will be used.

7.1. Literature Review

Related literatures from different sources (books, journals, Internet, etc.) will be reviewed to understand the existing hate speech detection methods.

7.2. Data Collection

To success this research data is collected from Facebook comment and posts in Afaan Oromo languages from popular Facebook pages. The dataset of hate speech is required for this research work of hate speech detection. So, the dataset is firstly the required step in the research work.

7.3. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is a data mining technique that involves transforming raw data into an understandable format. Real-world data is often incomplete, inconsistent, and/or lacking in certain behaviors or trends, and is likely to contain many errors. Data preprocessing is a proven method of resolving such issues. Data preprocessing prepares raw data for further processing.

7.4. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction involves reducing the amount of resources required to describe a large set of data. When performing analysis of complex data one of the major problem's stems from the number of variables involved. Analysis with a large number of variables generally requires a large amount of memory and computation power; also it may cause a classification algorithm to over fit to training samples and generalize poorly to new samples. Feature extraction is a general term for methods of constructing combinations of the variables to get around these problems while still describing the data with sufficient accuracy.

7.5. Development Tool

In this research work python 3.75 tool will be used as a development environment.

7.6. Model Training

The collected data were split into training sets and testing sets, to be used to train and validate the model respectively.

8. Research Plan

8.1. Budget Allocation

A budget is a financial expense used to decide what resources needed for research completion. It is an estimate of costs, and resources over a specified period, reflecting a reading of future financial conditions and goals. The resource planned will be allocated based on different requirements for the research will be completed. The following illustrates the amount of money and allocation of cost budget requirement.

No	Item	Quantity	Unit Price	Total price	Remark
1	Laptop	1	19,000birr	19,000Birr	
2	For Respondents	—	—	5000birr	
3	Mobile card	20	50	1000 birr	
4	Paper	3	90birr	270birr	
5	CD-RW	2	25birr	50birr	
6	Printing	—	—	600birr	
7	Flash-disk	1	250birr	250birr	
8	Pens	5	5birr	25birr	
9	Microsoft office 2019	—	free	free	Free download
10	Window 10	—	free	Free	
11	For Data collector	2	2000 birr	4000 birr	
12	Other expenses	—	10,000birr	10,000birr	
				Total Price=40,195	

Table 1: Budget Allocation for study

8.2. Time Schedule for Action Plan

An action plan is a document that lists what steps must be taken in order to achieve a specific goal. The purpose of an action plan is to clarify how long time is required to reach the goal, formulate a timeline for specific tasks need to be completed. The researcher wants to complete all his work according to his schedule.

ID	Task Name	Duration	May 2020				Jun 2020				Jul 2020				Aug 2020				Sep 2020				Oct 2020				Nov 2020				Dec 2020			
			5/3				6/7				7/5				8/2	8/9			9/6															
1	Literature review & proposal development	6.2w	■																															
2	Related work analysis	5.4w					■																											
3	Data collection and analysis	8.8w									■																							
4	Designing a models	6.6w													■																			
5	Prototype development	6.6w																	■															
6	Testing & evaluating the model	1.8w																					■											
7	Conclusion and recommendation	1.4w																					■											
8	Documentation	1.4w																					■											

Table 2: Time schedule for action plan

9. References

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